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Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu**ABSTRACT**

Teacher competence refers to the right way of conveying units of knowledge, application and skills to students. This paper also highlights the various competencies like use of appropriate techniques, efficacy in Teaching, effective use of Aids, rapport with students and colleagues, and catering to individual differences. The present study is undertaken to study the teaching competency of B.Ed. female teacher trainees. The major objective of the study is to find out the difference between (i) rural and urban (ii) Government and Self-financing college (iii) girls and Co-education College and (iv) Undergraduate, Postgraduate and M.Phil. degree B.Ed. female teacher trainees. The 148 samples were taken from the B.Ed. female teacher trainees who are studying in the ten colleges of education in thanjavur and pudukottai districts which are the colleges of education, affiliated to Tamil Nadu Teacher Education University, Chennai. The data were collected by Teaching Competency Scale standardized by Dorathi Rani (2000). Special attention was given to such factors like nature of college, type of college and degree of B.Ed. female teacher trainees. The data are analyzed by t-test and ANOVA. The results revealed that there is a significant difference between (i) urban and rural (ii) Government college and Self-financing college and (iii) girls college and Co-education College B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency and (iv) there is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. degree B.Ed. female teacher trainees.

Introduction

Education is the fundamental means of human development. By it the innate powers of human beings are developed, their knowledge skills and competencies are enhanced, and their behavior is changed, and they are made civilized and culture citizens. Teaching is a process, which usually takes place in the classroom situations. It is more of a formal process. In the classroom situations, we see that the teacher has something in his mind and he wants to convey it to the students. Competency is equipping the teacher with adequate knowledge and ideas to begin with profession career. Competency is the demonstration of knowledge skills and attitudes required to perform a given task or act. Teaching competency is the skill, ability and capabilities possessed by the teacher so as to make the teaching-learning environment effective and productive thereby realizing the full potential of teacher as well as students and in turn achieving the goals of education. According to Rama (1979) defines teacher competency as “the ability of a teacher manifested through a set of overt teacher classroom behaviors which is a resultant of the interaction between the presage and the product variables of teaching within a social setting”.

Significance of the Study

In National Policy on Education (1986) expected a lot from the teachers by putting a tremendous faith and responsibility on them, since it boldly opined, “no people can rise above the level of its teachers”. It further stated that, “status of the teacher reflects the socio cultural ethos of a society”. Secondary teacher education students are the teacher trainees who undergo a pre-service training on learning process that provides experiences for development towards good teaching. The National Curriculum Framework (2009) has described in

secondary teacher education, “the training of teachers happens in insular, intellectually impoverished environments that are severed from ground realities as well as the aims of education they espouse. Such an intellectual isolation activity discourages educational theorization and the growth of disciplinary and interdisciplinary enquiry”. Here the competency in teaching is equipping the teacher with adequate knowledge and ideas to begin with profession career and transformation of inborn or innate qualities and concealed or hidden strength of the individual into application (utility) of the B.Ed. female teacher trainees. The B.Ed. female teacher trainees have to identify the requisite skills, knowledge, competences and strategies to teach education and to equip all B.Ed. female teacher trainees with such skills, knowledge and competency so that a complete transformation will be possible. Belonging to the teaching community, one should be use of Appropriate Techniques, efficacy in Teaching, effective use of Aids, rapport with students and colleagues, and catering to individual differences, he can be considered as a competent teacher. Being very thoughtful of the above significance, the investigator prepared his mind to study the teaching competency of B.Ed. female teacher trainees.

Research Questions

- Is there any significant difference between rural and urban area B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency?
- Is there any significant difference among Government College and self-financing college B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency?
- Is there any significant difference among girls and Co-education College of education B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency?

- Is there any significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate, and M.Phil. Degree of B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between rural and urban area B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.
2. There is no significant difference among Government College and self-financing college B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.
3. There is no significant difference among girls and Co-education College of education B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.
4. There is no significant difference among Undergraduate, Postgraduate and M.Phil. Degree of B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.

Method

The investigator adopted survey method. The population for the present study consists of B.Ed. female teacher trainees who are studying in the colleges of education, Pudukkottai, Thanjavur Districts of Tamil Nadu State, South India.

Sample

The investigator has used stratified random sampling technique for collecting the data. The stratification has made on the basis of gender, locality of B.Ed. female teacher trainees, type of college, nature of college and degree of B.Ed. teacher trainees. The sample consists of 148 B.Ed. female teacher trainees from Government colleges and self-financing colleges in Pudukkottai and Thanjavur Districts of Tamil Nadu State, South India.

Tool

Teaching Competency Scale standardized by Dorathi Rani (2000) is used. This tool contains 70 items, each item being a statement followed by a five point scale: always, usually, sometimes, rarely and never. The investigator has studied the attributes of a good teacher and has framed a scale to measure the teaching competency of the teacher in five dimensions. They are namely use of Appropriate Techniques, efficacy in Teaching, effective use of Aids, rapport with students and colleagues, and catering to individual differences.

Analysis of Data

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between rural and urban area B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.

Table 1: Difference between Urban and Rural Area B.Ed. Female Teacher Trainees in Their Teaching Competency

Teaching Competency	Urban (N=35)		Rural (N=113)		t-value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Use of Appropriate Techniques	69.05	8.82	68.07	10.96	2.201	S
Efficacy in Teaching	99.83	15.49	97.56	14.50	0.017	NS
Effective Use of Aids	41.60	11.08	39.27	6.80	0.065	NS
Rapport with Students and Colleagues	56.65	5.46	53.00	9.00	5.698	S
Catering to Individual Differences	26.51	3.39	25.03	4.40	3.803	S
Teaching Competency	29.41	28.28	28.29	37.40	2.803	S

Use of Appropriate Techniques	69.05	8.82	68.07	10.96	2.201	S
Efficacy in Teaching	99.83	15.49	97.56	14.50	0.017	NS
Effective Use of Aids	41.60	11.08	39.27	6.80	0.065	NS
Rapport with Students and Colleagues	56.65	5.46	53.00	9.00	5.698	S
Catering to Individual Differences	26.51	3.39	25.03	4.40	3.803	S
Teaching Competency	29.41	28.28	28.29	37.40	2.803	S

Table-1 reveals that there is significant difference between urban and rural area B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their use of appropriate techniques, rapport with students and colleagues and catering to individual differences, as the calculated t-values 2.201, 5.698 and 3.803 are greater than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of significance. But there is no significant difference between urban and rural area B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their efficacy in teaching and effective use of aids, as the calculated t-values 0.017 and 0.065 are less than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of significance. In general there is a significant difference among B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency, as the calculated t-value 2.803 are greater than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the urban area B.Ed. female teacher trainees are better in their teaching competency than the rural area B.Ed. female teacher trainees. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference among Government College and self-financing college B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.

Table 2: Difference between Government and Self-Financing College B.Ed. Female Teacher Trainees in their Teaching Competency

Teaching Competency	Government (N=26)		Self-financing (N=122)		t-value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Use of Appropriate Techniques	68.65	8.37	68.23	10.89	3.508	S
Efficacy in Teaching	99.11	13.74	98.02	14.98	0.321	NS
Effective Use of Aids	39.19	6.60	39.95	8.33	0.055	NS
Rapport with Students and Colleagues	51.42	9.15	54.39	8.21	0.003	NS
Catering to Individual Differences	25.65	3.67	25.32	4.34	1.392	NS
Teaching Competency	28.40	29.33	28.59	36.99	2.938	S

Table-2 shows that there is no significant difference between Govt. college and Self-financing college B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their efficacy in teaching, effective use of aids, rapport with students and colleagues and catering to individual differences, as the calculated t-values 0.321, 0.055, 0.003 and 1.392 are less than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of

significance. But there is significant difference between Government and Self-financing college B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their use of appropriate techniques, as the calculated t -value 3.508 is greater than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of significance. In general there is significant difference between Government and Self-financing college B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching, as the calculated t -value 2.938 is greater than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the self-financing college B.Ed. female teacher trainees are better in their teaching competency than the Government college B.Ed. female teacher trainees. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference among Girls College and Co-education College of education B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.

Table 3: Difference between Girls College and Co-Education College B.Ed. Female Teacher Trainees in their Teaching Competency

Teaching Competency	Girls College (N=20)		Co-education College (N=128)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Use of Appropriate Techniques	71.20	10.85	67.85	10.38	0.033	NS
Efficacy in Teaching	99.90	12.87	97.95	15.03	0.358	NS
Effective Use of Aids	38.60	7.79	40.01	8.09	0.457	NS
Rapport with Students and Colleagues	52.05	11.34	54.15	7.89	7.794	S
Catering to Individual Differences	25.30	5.15	25.39	4.09	3.673	S
Teaching Competency	28.70	43.42	28.53	34.52	3.238	S

(At 5% level of significance, the tab 25.39le value of 't' is 1.96)

It is learnt from the Table-3 presents there is no significant difference between Girls College and Co-education College B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their use of appropriate techniques, efficacy in teaching and effective use of aids, as the calculated t -values 0.033, 0.358 and 0.457 are less than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of significance. But there is significant difference between Girls College and co-education college B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their rapport with students and colleagues and catering to individual differences, as the calculated t -values 7.794 and 3.673 are greater than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of significance. In general there is significant difference between Girls College and co-education college B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency, as the calculated t -value 3.238 is greater than the table value 1.96 at five percent level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the girls' college B.Ed. female teacher trainees are better in their teaching competency than the

co-education college B.Ed. female teacher trainees. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate, and M.Phil. degree of B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.

Table 4: F-value among Under Graduate, Post Graduate and M.Phil. Degree B.Ed. Female Teacher Trainees in their Teaching Competency

Teaching Competency	Sum of Variations	Sum of Squares	MSV	'F' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Use of Appropriate Techniques	Between	261.18	130.59	1.193	NS
	Within	15868.51	109.43		
Efficacy in teaching	Between	366.94	183.47	0.843	NS
	Within	31566.14	217.69		
Effective use of aids	Between	0.160	0.080	0.001	NS
	Within	9515.27	65.62		
Rapport with students and colleagues	Between	126.104	63.05	0.886	NS
	Within	10320.45	71.17		
Catering to individual differences.	Between	7.463	3.73	0.206	NS
	Within	2621.58	18.08		
Teaching Competency	Between	1951.13	975.56	0.764	NS
	Within	185272.13	1277.73		

(At 5% level of significance for 2, 145df the table value of 'F' is 2.996)

From the data on table-4, it can be seen that there is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. degree B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their use of appropriate techniques, efficacy in teaching, effective use of aids, rapport with students and colleagues and catering to individual differences, as the calculated 'F' values 1.193, 0.843, 0.001, 0.886 and 0.206 are less than the table value 2.996 at five percent level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the M.Phil. degree B.Ed. female teacher trainees are better use of appropriate techniques, efficacy in teaching, effective use of aids, rapport with students and colleagues and catering to individual differences than the undergraduate and post graduate degree B.Ed. female teacher trainees. In general there is no significant difference among the undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. Degree B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency, as the calculated 'F' value 0.764 is less than the table value 2.996 at five percent level of significance. Hence null hypothesis is rejected.

Findings

1. The t -test result reveals that there is a significant difference between (i) urban and rural area, (ii) Government college and Self-financing College and (iii) girls college and Co-education College B.Ed. female teacher trainees in their teaching competency.
2. The 'F' test result reveals that there is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. Degree B.Ed. female teacher trainees.

Discussions and Conclusion

The present study clearly indicated that the teaching competency of B.Ed. female teacher trainees are unique in their use of appropriate techniques, efficacy in teaching, effective use of aids, rapport with students and colleagues and catering to individual differences and teaching competency. The above findings of the present study is supported by the results of the investigation made by Antony Gracious and Annaraja (2011) revealed that there was significant difference between rural and urban B.Ed. teacher trainees in their teaching competency, while comparing the mean scores, urban area B.Ed. teacher trainees are better than rural area B.Ed. teacher trainees in their teaching competency. Likewise, the results of the investigation made by Sukla Roy Choudhary and Susanta Roy Chowdhury (2015) examined that there was significant difference between urban and rural area teacher educators in their teaching competency, while comparing mean scores, the urban area teacher educators are better in their teaching competency than the rural area teacher educators. On contrary, Jagannadh (2012) indicated that there was no significant difference between rural and urban teachers in terms of teaching competency and attitude towards teaching profession. *Jarrar Ahmad and Mohd. Ahmad Khan (2016)* examined that the Government and Private secondary school teachers are differ significantly on the measure of Teaching Competency. It is conclude that the B.Ed. college teacher trainees adopt appropriate teaching techniques, by using effective teaching aids, establish workable rapport with students and colleagues, attempt to cater to the learner's needs given the individual differences as to enhance their teaching competency. The B.Ed. college female teacher trainees have more interest on subject-knowledge, concern and care for the students and enduring patience with the slow-learners and making it more motivational and practical in the view, needs and requirements of the school students as well as in the present scenario of the society.

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